

Recommendations for conducting an interview

In the Feel phase, before starting to solve the detected problem, it is necessary to **understand** what is happening in the focus of action and how it is happening; both from one's own point of view and from the point of view of the people who interact in that focus.

This phase is very important because we have a **widespread habit of moving directly from the problem to the solution**. By using the DFC Methodology, we make a parenthesis that allows us to **understand the problem from different points of view**. In this way, we avoid applying a cognitive bias, the result of our experience, when solving the identified problem.

The objectives of the research are:

- **To ensure that we do not solve the wrong problem.**
- **To systematise the way we listen to other people**, who will also be affected by the solution we are going to propose, learning from them to better understand the environment and their needs for change.

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INTERVIEW

Interviews are used to inspire our solutions. We need to **understand how people relate to the focus of action.**

It is recommended that interviews are done **in pairs** for practical reasons: one person asks questions and the other notes down everything: **what is said and what is seen** (the interviewee's attitude towards the questions, body language, etc.). They can also be recorded and then transcribed, always asking prior permission and explaining what the information will be used for.

Making **a guide** is very useful for designing the interview, to avoid forgetting to write something down or overlooking a nuance. To construct it, it is advisable that, on a sheet of paper, you answer these 3 questions (in relation to the research objectives):

1. What do we know?
2. What do we think we know?
3. What don't we know and would like to know?

Then turn the paper over and divide the space into **five parts** to be filled in:

1st part: **Brief description** of the person to be interviewed → Pre-interview

2nd part: **Questions** I want to ask → Prior to the interview

3rd part: **Information** you have conveyed that **you didn't know** → During the interview

4th part: **Information** they have told me **that has surprised me** (and may become action points) → During the interview

5th part: **Doubts** that have remained **unresolved** or that have arisen for me afterwards → After the interview

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Keep in mind that:

- An interview is not a survey, it is a **conversation**.
- We don't want answers to closed questions that can be answered with yes or no. Try to ask **questions that encourage the person to express themselves**. In any case, if they answer with a terse yes or no, ask "why yes or why no", here you will discover the essence of their behaviour.
- We want the person we are going to interview to meet **certain criteria**, according to the objectives of the interview. If you find a person who doesn't meet them, you may not have to interview that person.
- We want them to tell us stories and anecdotes to **understand what is going on**, what they think, how they act and why.
- We must **collect the answers as they are expressed**, without interpreting them, completely verbatim.
- The **interviewer's attitude** is unique: **listen, listen and listen**.
- During the interview, the guide is basically just that: a guide. The interview should **flow**, always **keeping in mind our objectives** and the information we are looking for. If a question comes up in the course of the conversation, write it down and ask it when you see the opportunity.
- While researching, it is important to maintain an **observational and learning attitude** so as not to take information for granted; it is not about waiting for the interviewee to validate your own opinions and/or ideas.
- At this point, it is better to waste ingenuity in **questioning and probing** than to venture into assumptions or interpretations.
- We **do not judge the interviewee's comments**, whether they fit us or not.
- We don't look for data, we look for **relevant information**. Data is another source of information that has to be interpreted to become qualitative information.

The structure of the interview is as follows:

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Introduction: introduction by you and explanation of what you are doing the interview for.

Warm-up: to break the ice and generate confidence, talking about your previous experience in that context, looking for anecdotes. We will go from the general to the particular, starting from simplicity, diving into the boot of memories... In this way, we will continue to build trust. Remember that to answer the questions it is not necessary to build an argument from scratch; you are collecting life stories.

Deepening: in this part we will ask about more motivational, aspirational and philosophical aspects of our framework, using the information gathered earlier (if possible) as a "perch" (introduction). We are interested in how our user defines and understands them. This part is more complex and requires more attention for the interviewer and the interviewee, because the **interviewer has to be aware of how to continue** if a thread to pull on appears **or how to modify the question to inspire** the interviewee if he/she gets stuck. And **the interviewee has to travel inside him/herself to give answers**. It is necessary to know how to endure silences during interviews, as our interlocutor often needs to assimilate the question and construct the answer. Very interesting information can emerge from a well-sustained silence.

Closing: space for the interviewee to add whatever he/she feels necessary and a moment to **thank** him/her for his/her collaboration.

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